

Empirical analysis of potential improvements for high voltage protective algorithms

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1.-Introduction

This paper aims to explain the work developed and methodology followed within Task 4.2 of Work Package 4 (WP4) of EU funded MIGRATE – Massive InteGRATion of Power Electronic devices project for the assessment of short circuit protection relays under high penetration of renewable energies and power electronic devices. This task was developed during last year 2017. The benchmark test grid for this purpose, including detailed power electronics models, has been developed in RTDS environment in order to perform hardware in the loop tests. The analysis of the tests, which showed potential undesired behaviors of distance protection, are explained in the following paper, and are the focus of further research actions in WP4 studies.

By making use of hardware in the loop platforms distance, line differential and ground directional overcurrent protection functions, running in real protection devices have been tested and thoroughly analyzed. These functions were chosen due to their wide employability in transmission systems as primary and/or backup protection functions.

Security and stability of the system under fault conditions depends on the correct performance of the aforementioned protection functions. Therefore, it becomes critical to analyze if such protection algorithms, which have been so far designed for a power system mainly fed by synchronous generators, may experience difficulties and consequently jeopardize the system security when increasing the penetration level of renewable energy, asynchronously connected to the system.

To achieve the presented goals:

- a) Testing of real protection relays commonly employed by TSO's were carried out in RTDS platforms.
- b) Such tests were performed in scenarios with increasing penetration levels of renewable energies, comparing the protection relay behaviors with the ones obtained in the basis scenario (100% synchronous generation).
- c) Analysis of the results obtained were performed by means of automatic tools developed within the project and specific oscillography downloaded from each protection relay.

2.- Testing environment

The behavior of four protection relays from different manufacturers (A, B, C and D) has been assessed under different penetration levels of renewable energy. The operation of these relays has been evaluated in different locations of the benchmark network. The location of the relays (and their associated current and voltage transformers) are depicted in Figure 1 with blue rings.

Bus 13 is the grid equivalent that represents the slack bus for the simulation. As a reference for all the converters, it remain always connected during tests. This grid equivalent provides the voltage reference for the renewable generator models (Type 3 and Type 4 wind turbines and PV generator) and HVDC and consumes the excess of power provided by each renewable generator and not consumed by the loads.

Figure 1. Benchmark model with CTs remarked [1]

As shown in Figure 1, the lines chosen to evaluate the behavior of protection relays are:

- **Line 5-7:** with the tests along this line, the behavior of **protection functions are assessed based on the Type 4 Wind Turbine behavior**. The model used includes all the lines connected, as shown in Figure 1. “Grid Side” bus is bus 5 while “Renewable Side” is bus 7.
- **Line 4-5:** with the tests along this line, the behavior of **protection functions are assessed based on the PV generator behavior**. For the studies related to this line, line 1-5 is disconnected. Due to this disconnection, the whole (and only) current contribution seen by protection located at bus 5 during faults is provided from line 5-7. “Grid Side” bus is bus 4 while “Renewable Side” is bus 5.
- **Line 4-6:** with the tests along this line, the behavior of **protection functions are assessed based on the Type 3 Wind Turbine behavior**. For the studies within this line, line 1-4 is disconnected. “Grid Side” bus is bus 4 while “Renewable Side” is bus 6.

In order to evaluate relay operation, analog (voltage and currents) and digital (trip, breaker status, reclose) signals must be exchanged between the benchmark model built in RTDS and each of the relays in a Hardware in the Loop environment. In the following sections, the considerations needed to perform the study are included. Figure 2 shows signal exchange between protection device under test and RTDS/Signal amplifiers.

Figure 2. Hardware in the loop testing. Laboratory test-bench and signals exchanged

RTDS is able to store its oscillography results in COMTRADE files. These COMTRADE files save relevant information for the analysis of the behavior of protection relays under the different test conditions.

- Signals collected:
 - o Analog signals: Voltages measured at 400 kV level for buses 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 13. Voltage and currents in MV level for buses 8, 9 and 10. Currents measured at lines: 1-2, 3-4, 4-6, 4-5, 5-7, 1-5, 1-4 and from the slack bus. Tripping and reclose times.
 - o Digital signals: Tripping and reclose digital signals received from protection relays.
- Duration of the oscillography: The fault duration is set to 2.0 seconds to study possible problems with protection relays. Based on this fault duration, the length of the oscillography in RTDS is set to 2.5 seconds.
- Time between fault inception and the protection trip (tripping time) and time between trip and reclose are registered (reclosing time). According to these values, it is possible to identify and classify the behavior of the protection function under the different test conditions.

3.- Cases of study

Once the network under study and the testing platform is presented, the conditions fixed for the tests are listed below:

- Negative sequence current injected by HVDC, PV and Type 4 Wind Turbine is equal to zero [2] [3] [4] [5]. This condition is considered as the most restrictive from the point of view of protection relay performance.
- Protection functions to be analyzed:
 - Distance protection
 - Differential protection
 - Ground directional overcurrent

Protection algorithms implemented on 4 different platforms (real protection relays) are studied.

- Lines where the protection relays are installed (in the network shown in Figure 1):
 - Line 5-7
 - Line 4-6
 - Line 4-5
- Scenarios defined:
 - Strong network: With Only synchronous generators, only renewable generators (always with the grid equivalent as slack bus) and intermediate scenario.
 - Weak network: With Only synchronous generators, only renewable generators and one intermediate scenario.

	R_p	X_p (L_p)	R_{p0}	X_{p0} (L_{p0})
Strong Network	30.319 Ω	6.795 Ω (0.02163 H)	85.864 Ω	6.894 Ω (0.02194 H)
Weak Network	158.413 Ω	34.595 Ω (0.11012 H)	328.570 Ω	35.375 Ω (0.11260 H)

Table 1. Parameters of R/L for strong and weak network

- Generation level from renewables: 40 MW and 200 MW.
 - Current contribution during fault: Control for limiting the negative sequence current in the steady state of the fault is set. Therefore, full converter topologies provide only positive sequence current. Besides, this current is limited to 1.1 p.u. approximately in PV and Type 4 wind turbine.
 - Type 3 Wind Turbine does not present the full converter topology and injects negative sequence current to minimize 2ω oscillations.
- Generation level from synchronous: 40 MW and 170 MW.
- Point of the line where the fault is applied depends on the protection function under test:
 - Distance protection: 0 % (forward and backward), 50.0 %, 70.0 %, 90.0 % and 100 % (forward and backward). Additionally, a repetitiveness of three times per point of the line is applied to check the consistency of the result.
 - Differential protection: Two faults inside (65 and 95 %) the line and one more outside the protected element.

- Ground directional overcurrent protection: Since 67N is a backup protection function, same points than used for distance protection tests are tested in order to ensure that in the case that distance protection does not operate as expected, 67N represents a reliable backup protection function.
- Type of fault: Single line to ground, line to line, line to line to ground and three-phase.
- Value of the fault resistance: Bolt faults are applied initially for distance. 150 ohm are applied for phase to ground faults to line differential and ground directional overcurrent functions. If the fault resistance results too high to obtain the voltage polarization needed for ground directional overcurrent, the fault resistance is reduced to 75 ohm.

4.- Definition of testing logics

In protection philosophy of transmission lines, main protection 1 or main protection 2 trip the breaker without considering the behavior of the other protection. That is, the combined performance of main 1 and main 2 behaves as a LOGICAL “OR” gate. In the case of the tests carried out for performing the analyses needed for the presented study, such “OR” gate is not interesting, because in the case that the main protection does not act and backup protection operates (or vice-versa), a possible problem which should be analyzed could remain hidden.

In the RTDS test bench defined for this study two main protections are connected in parallel in each side of the protected line but, as mentioned above, not using an “OR” gate for the trip signals. Using such “OR” logic, the protection relay that needs more time to trip would not emit trip signal since the breaker would have opened when the first trip signal is applied. Thus, with this philosophy, we would lose information about the behavior of one protection, the one which acts slower.

Therefore, with the aim of not losing information about the behavior of protection relays connected in parallel, “AND” logic gates have been used to trip and reclose the circuit breakers. With these logic gates, the breaker opens only when trip signals coming from both protection relays are received.

Consequently, if one of the protection relays does not send trip signal, the breaker remains closed and the fault applied. In this way, the user is able to analyze the difference between tripping times of each protection. The same logic is followed for the reclose signal.

The trip scheme described can be observed in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Trip scheme programmed in RTDS

5.-Breaker status at grid-side positions

As it is explained above, the presented study aims to analyze behavior of distance, line differential and ground directional overcurrent functions under scenarios based on high penetration levels of renewable energies and power electronic converters. However, due to present state of the art limitations is not possible to remove totally the traditional synchronous behavior of the slack equivalent

bus, otherwise control algorithms of power electronics of renewable generation systems do not operate correctly, since they need a voltage source reference to be synchronized and inject power into the grid.

Accordingly, protections located at bus 5 for line 5-7 tests, at bus 4 for line 4-6 tests and at bus 4 for line 4-5 tests always see a conventional (synchronous generator-based) current contribution to the fault. It has been analyzed that the protections at these nodes operate correctly with the settings provided to the laboratories, thus tripping the associated breakers in short times. However, from the point of view of the analysis of what protection relays in the renewable side see under the current contribution from renewables, the trip of the grid side breaker has been blocked as from a TSO perspective is not the aim to evaluate the operation of PE devices during islanded mode.

In the case that breaker at grid side position trips, renewable generators would remain connected in islanded mode. In this case, two situations may occur:

- First situation occurs when the voltage in the line, due to the breaker disconnection at grid side position, goes below the Low Voltage Ride Through limit set in the control system of each renewable generator. In this case, the control system would disconnect the renewable generator. Therefore, protection relay would not see the current contribution from renewable source after this disconnection. If the protection does not trip before the disconnection, it never acts due to this lack of current. Therefore, a non-trip would be obtained but without enough time to be sure about the behavior of the relay. Thus, under this situation the test would be considered incomplete and results not relevant.
- The second situation is what happens if the voltage goes down after the trip of the remote breaker, but this drop is not sufficient to cause a disconnection due to the LVRT control. It is certainly possible that this situation occurs due to the reactive current injection during the fault due to the voltage support requirements based on grid codes. To have a clearer idea about what may happen, this is the sequence of events that should be avoided:
 - a) Protection relay installed at grid side position detects the fault and trips. This trip usually lasts at least 70-90 ms (20-30 ms for tripping decision of the protection relay and 50-60 ms for the breaker opening time).
 - b) During these 4-5 cycles, the control of the renewable has already reacted and the control mode for voltage dips has been activated. This control mode must provide voltage support due to the fault condition according to the grid code requirements. The bigger the voltage drop in the grid, the bigger reactive current support from the renewables based on these requirements.
 - c) This voltage support based on reactive power injection may cause that, when the remote breaker opens (breaker at grid side position) the voltage may not be below the LVRT limit and, consequently, the renewable remains connected temporarily.
 - d) Under this situation, the renewable generator cannot follow the voltage reference fixed by the slack bus and it remains connected in islanded mode. Since this situation is not in the scope of the task and controls of the generators are not prepared to detect this situation, the control system would probably lose the stability¹.
 - e) This non-controlled mode may cause non-stable current and voltage waveforms. Under these conditions, the behavior of the protection (trip or lack of trip emission) cannot be considered relevant nor reliable because tests conditions are not controlled.

¹ Nevertheless, WT installed are equipped with anti-island detectors. Under this situation, the WT would be disconnected, fault current would disappear, so the protection may not detect the fault situation.

Therefore, since this study aims to know how present algorithms and settings criteria behave under high penetration level of renewables, breaker at grid side position remains always closed (emulating a breaker failure) during distance protection and ground directional overcurrent tests. This method for testing ensures that protection relays at renewable bus side see the fault contribution during all the fault duration at the same time that the renewable generators do not lose the voltage reference provided by the slack bus. Accordingly, for each line the following considerations are defined:

- For line 5-7 protection relay acts over the breaker located at bus 7 position (breaker failure over the breaker at bus 5 position)
- For line 4-6 protection relay acts over the breaker located at bus 6 position (breaker failure over the breaker at bus 4 position)
- For line 4-5 protection relay acts over the breaker located at bus 5 position (breaker failure over the breaker at bus 4 position).

6.- Automation for testing

In order to make the study feasible, as well as replicable, it is necessary to develop ad-hoc tools for applying automatically the huge amount of tests derived from the cases of study above explained. Script codes for RTDS have been developed in order to deal with this number of tests and to ensure that tests done in TUDELFT and CIRCE were performed under identical conditions (Figure 4). It is remarkable that along with changing test conditions according to test cases defined, the script performs an automated initial fault analysis in order to identify relevant situations to be studied in deeper detail.

Figure 4. Advantages of scripting

Next are described the steps followed to perform and automate the tests.

1. The tests start with transmission line 5-7, then line 4-6 and finally line 4-5.
2. On each line, distance protection is tested first, then differential and finally ground directional overcurrent.
3. Manufacturers A and B are tested in CIRCE. Manufacturers C and D are tested in TU Delft. The tests are done at the same time to be able to compare the results obtained.
4. The scripts perform the different tests changing automatically the parameters, and classifying automatically the behavior of the protection system. Script files provide the following information:
 - a. Excel file (one file for each side of the line under test, example Figure 5), including:

- i. Number of test
- ii. The type of the fault: Single-Line to ground, line to line, line to line to ground and three phase.
- iii. The generation scenario: Synchronous, renewable or the combination of both for weak and strong grid defined in the slack bus conditions.
- iv. The point of the line (in %) where the fault is applied.
- v. Trip signal reception from the two protection devices phase A, B and C tested in each laboratory.
- vi. Reclose signal reception from the two protection devices tested in each laboratory.
- vii. Tripping time associated to the trip signals. Four tripping times in total: one for each protection device at each side of the protection line. The timer starts when the fault is applied and finishes when the trip signal is received.
- viii. Reclosing time associated to the reclose signal received. The timer starts when the breaker is opened (at least one of their poles) and finishes when the reclose signal is received from the protection.

Point of the fault	Type of fault	Generation level	Scenario	Trip_A	Trip_B	Trip_C	Close	Behaviour			tripping				reclose									
								not expected	Delayed trip	Under reach	Over reach	time Prot_A	time Prot_A	tripping time Prot_B	reclose time Prot_B	TripA Prot_A	TripB Prot_A	TripC Prot_A	Reclose Prot_A	TripA Prot_B	TripB Prot_B	TripC Prot_B	Reclose Prot_B	
5.0%	SLG	40MW	SG_SG	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.025	1.042	0.026		1.022	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
5.0%	SLG	200MW	SG_SG	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.025	1.042	0.026		1.023	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
5.0%	SLG	40MW	SG_WG	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.025	1.036	0.027		1.022	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
5.0%	SLG	200MW	SG_WG	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.025	1.038	0.025		1.025	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
50.0%	SLG	40MW	SG_SG	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0.025	1.039	0.038		1.024	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
50.0%	SLG	200MW	SG_SG	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.026	1.030	0.026		1.020	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
50.0%	SLG	40MW	SG_WG	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0.026	1.040	0.037		1.021	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
50.0%	SLG	200MW	SG_WG	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.026	1.030	0.023		1.022	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1

Figure 5. Example of information gathered in the Excel File (protection manufacturer A and B). Synchronous generation and strong/weak grid

The information saved at the excel sheet provide information to the user about which tests have not obtained an expected result. In this way, the user is able to filter those results most interesting to repeat and analyze by means of protection oscillography download.

The test is considered *passed* if all the following conditions are accomplished:

- The protection trips within the expected time [6]:
 - For distance protection:
 - Fault within zone 1: Less than 45 ms
 - Fault within zone 2: Between 400 ms and 440 ms
 - For differential protection:
 - Fault inside the protected line: Less than 45 ms
 - For directional protection:
 - Fault forward in the time defined by settings. The setting is fixed time: 200 ms for first step and 600 ms for second step of setting.
- The protection does not trip when:
 - For distance protection:
 - Fault backwards
 - For differential protection:

- Fault outside the line
- For directional protection
 - Fault backwards
 - The pole operation of the protection works correctly. A correct behavior is considered when the protection relay opens the correct pole (or poles) of the breaker, depending on if the fault is single-phase, phase to phase or three-phase.
 - The reclose cycle works correctly. A correct behavior is considered when:
- For distance protection:
 - Reclose cycle is performed when the fault is inside zone 1.
 - The reclose time is equal to 1 second (time between trip order and reclose order), both in single pole and three pole operation of the breaker.
- For differential protection:
 - Reclose cycle is performed when the fault is inside the protected line.
 - The reclose time is equal to 1 second, both with single pole and three-pole operation.
- For directional protection:
 - Reclose must not occur.

In other circumstances, the test is considered *failed* and the oscillography data is saved.

7.-Initial validation of settings

Before starting with mass tests to assess protection performance under high penetration of renewables, initial validation is applied with synchronous generation. The objective of this initial validation is to guarantee that the protection function and its settings are working properly with a classical synchronous generation scenario. After this validation, a base case to compare with protection performance under high renewable penetration scenario is obtained.

For the initial validation of settings for distance protection, the following tests are done using the line 5-7:

- Scenario: Strong and weak network with 100% synchronous generation.
- Type of faults to be applied:
 - Single line to ground (AG):
 - Point of the line: 0% and 50 %
 - Point of the wave: 0 and 90 degrees
 - Fault resistance: 15 ohm
 - Line to line (AB):
 - Point of the line: 0% and 50 %
 - Point of the wave: 0 and 90 degrees
 - Fault resistance: 10 ohm

These test parameters used for validation of distance protection are based on IEC 62055-121:2014 standard for distance protection testing and this conditions apply for radial configurations with current supplied from only one side with the other side without contribution. According to this statement, this way of testing suits for protection relay located at grid side position but not for relay located at

synchronous or renewable generator side protection. I.e., according to the network topology, validation according to the standard is applied to a fault inside line 5-7 with protection seeing the current provided by the grid side (bus 5). This validation for grid side according to the IEC 62055-121:2014 Standard is applied only once, since the criteria followed for grid side protection relay is always the same.

Once this validation is done, the process followed with the three lines under test is based on the comparison of protection relay behavior between the scenarios with only synchronous and with renewable generators based on power electronic converters.

For the "*generator side*" the validation of the settings is done by comparison of the renewable scenario results with synchronous generator behavior. That is, for each line, there is a base scenario with only synchronous generators connected. With the settings provided by REE, based on usual settings calculation practices, to TUDELFT and CIRCE laboratories, the behavior of the protection must be:

- For distance protection: Faults within zone 1 must be tripped in less than 45 ms. Faults in zone 2 must be tripped in less than 440 ms.
- For line differential protection: Faults inside the line must be tripped in less than 45 ms. Faults outside the protected line must not trip.
- For ground directional overcurrent: Line to Line faults and three phase faults must not make the protection trip since there is no ground current flowing. Single line to ground and line to line to ground faults must be tripped by the protection, since there is ground current flowing. There are two different tripping times set which depend on the current value through the neutral point.
- Once the protection relays are working correctly with 100% synchronous scenario, the base case for the comparison to the renewable scenario is established.

Settings for A, B, C and D protection relays are sent by REE to CIRCE and TUDELFT laboratories. Settings values for each protection depend on the line parameters and current contribution. For calculating these settings, a CAPE model is used as auxiliary tool to help this setting calculation for each line of the model. Settings are made according to TSO Criteria used on their own lines for protection. That is, settings used are in line with present practices in the industry.

Validation of the settings is performed with synchronous generation, firstly the tests are done for distance (solid faults), line differential (150 ohm phase to ground resistance) and ground directional overcurrent (150 ohm phase to ground) only with synchronous generators connected and renewable ones disconnected). These first results with only synchronous generation must accomplish the actuation times for distance (zone 1 and zone 2), line differential (tripping faults inside and no tripping faults outside) and ground directional overcurrent (tripping faults involving ground and no tripping faults isolated from ground).

The initial validation of the settings is applied to the line 5-7. Results obtained are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Results for settings validation in grid side position based on IEC 62055-121:2014. Distance protection

Type of fault	Point of the Voltage wave	Fault resistance	Point of the line	Synch. Generation level	Grid conditions	Relay A Relay B Relay C Relay D
SLG	0 and 90 degrees	15 ohm	0% and 50 %	40, 200 MW	Strong and weak grid, synchronous generation	Correct behavior. Zone 1 trip in less than 35 ms.
SLG	0 and 90 degrees	15 ohm	100% ²	40, 200 MW	Strong and weak grid, synchronous generation	Correct behavior. Zone 2 trip in less than 440 ms.
LL	0 and 90 degrees	10 ohm	0% and 50%	40, 200 MW	Strong and weak grid, synchronous generation	Correct behavior. Zone 1 trip in less than 35 ms.
LL	0 and 90 degrees	10 ohm	100%	40, 200 MW	Strong and weak grid, synchronous generation	Correct behavior. Zone 2 trip in less than 440 ms.

According to the results shown in Table 2, the following conclusions were obtained:

- Results obtained for grid side position relays according to the standard conditions for testing are correct.
- Settings criteria for distance protection are considered correct.
- The final validation of the settings for each line and protection function is done independently. Before starting to test scenarios with high penetration of renewable energies and power electronics, each protection is tested with synchronous generation scenario. This result is the base-case for all the study (that is the reference case). Once the behavior is considered correct for synchronous generation scenario, with the same settings, tests with renewables can be applied.
- Fault resistance used for the tests:
 - o For distance protection: Solid fault.
 - o For line differential protection: 150 ohm fault phase to ground faults.
 - o For ground directional overcurrent protection: 150 ohm phase to ground faults. This fault resistance can be reduced to the half (75 ohm) if the polarizing voltage is not sufficient for the activation of the protection function.

Once the protection operates correctly with synchronous generators, there is already a base case where the protection relays are working correctly. This case is compared with the protection relay behavior in the case of connecting renewable generators instead of synchronous.

² This additional case was included to have an additional point of test in zone 2 of the distance protection

7.-Summary and main issues found

This paper explains the methodology followed for conducting the study, in real-time, of protection relay behavior under high penetration of renewable energies scenarios.

Near 17000 tests were registered with the script and excel file tools described in previous sections. This results allow WP4 of MIGRATE project to analyze possible future problems of protection algorithms (distance, line differential and ground directional overcurrent) under high penetration of renewable generator topologies.

Throughout the study, these were the main issues found:

- Distance protection presents a significant number of non-expected results, including wrong trips or delayed trips, therefore this function will be the focus of further research actions in MIGRATE WP4 studies. The main conclusions related to distance protection performance are the following:
 - o Faulted phase selection, directionality declaration and impedance measurement during the initial instants of fault occurrence have been identified as main causes of the non-expected results (missed trips, overreach, delayed trips...). Therefore, these will be the three pillars of further investigations.
 - o The lack of negative sequence current contribution under unbalanced faults and the fast time response of the converters are important factors for the performance of protections in scenarios with high penetration level of renewable energies, and have strong influence in the problems mentioned in the previous point. Therefore, along with protection algorithms, control strategies of PE devices should be taken into account for further analyses.
- Line differential protection shows good behavior for all the tests performed. However, this protection function fully relies on fiber optic communication schemes and, due to the necessary communication infrastructure, has a high economic impact that must be considered by utilities. Future tests, considering scenarios with 100% PE generators, even without the Slack bus connected (synchronous type current contribution), should be made in order to completely assess the behavior of line differential protection.
- Ground differential overcurrent protection shows also good results during the test process. However, this is a backup function only for grounded faults, not for line to line and three phase faults. Therefore, considering the distance protection problems previously described and the line differential protection is only able to operate for faults inside the protected element, not providing backup for external faults; additional backup action would be needed for line-to-line and three phase faults. Especially considering that neither overcurrent nor directional overcurrent will be able to detect faults with the short circuit levels of networks in which high penetration of PE generators is expected as they will not be able to distinguish between normal and faulty conditions.

More detailed analysis of results are explained in specific papers for Type 3 and Type 4 Wind Turbines. [7].

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Disclaimer

This paper reflects the MIGRATE consortium's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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